

SURFACE MODIFICATION FOR CONDUCTIVE BALLS WITH CARBON NANOTUBES AND GOLD NANOPARTICLES

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Keywords: *Conductive particles, Gold nanoparticles, CNT-metal nanoparticle composites*

1 Introduction

The emergence of compact, flexible electronics leads to great interest in conductive films which enable to electrically interconnect IC chips to substrates with low-temperature process. The films consist of electro-conducting micro- and nano-sized particles dispersed in an insulating polymer matrix. Most of commercialized conductive balls are metal plated polymer beads, but the plating steps have some serious drawbacks: low cost efficiency and difficulties in getting individually and uniformly plated particles [1]. Furthermore, the use of rare earth metal (e. g. gold and silver) causes the high cost problems. Many researchers have tried to overcome these shortcomings by reducing the thickness of plated metal layers and by depositing gold nanoparticles on the surface of polymer particles rather than the electro-plating methods [1, 2]. The latter method makes the process simple and eco-friendly, however it requires additional electroless plating.

In this study, we designed and fabricated gold nanoparticles (goldNPs) decorated CNT/polystyrene (goldNPs/CNT/PS) conducting balls with low metal concentration through scalable process. We expect that CNT layers on the surface of microspheres can facilitate the formation of conducting path way and the adhesion of gold nanoparticles. Also, it is well known that hybridization of CNTs and goldNPs results in successful integration of the electrical and mechanical properties [3]. To reduce pretreatment process of polymer surface, CNTs were mechano-chemically coated on the surface of polymer spheres in dry coating process and the goldNPs were covalently attached on the CNT surfaces by the interaction between Au and thiol group on the CNT surfaces.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The multi-walled carbon nanotubes used in this study were synthesized by a chemical vapor deposition method (purchased by Hanwha NanoTech Co., Ltd). Sulfuric acid H₂SO₄, nitric acid HNO₃, Cysteamine (NH₂(CH₂)₂SH), tri-sodium citrate, N, N'-Dicyclohexyl carbodiimide (DCC), (3-mercaptopropyl)tri-methoxysilane (HS(CH₂)₃Si(OCH₃)₃, silane coupling agent), Gold (III) chloride trihydrate (HAuCl₄·H₂O) were purchased from Aldrich.

2.2 Preparation of CNTs/PS conducting particles

2.2.1 Preparation of s-CNTs

Pristine MWCNTs were carboxylated by chemical oxidation in a 3:1 mixture (v/v) of sulfuric acid and nitric acid at 70°C with vigorous stirring for 3h. The acid treated MWCNTs (a-CNTs) are neutralized by washing and filtering with deionized water. The a-CNTs were dispersed in DMF under 2hr ultra sonication, followed by the addition of DCC and cysteamine. The system was left under continuous bath sonication at 60°C for 24hr. During the thiolation reaction, the carboxyl groups on MWCNTs chemically reacted with amine groups of cysteamine and this hydrolysis reaction created amide bonds. The thiolation synthetic method is similar to that employed by Choong Kyun Rhee and co-workers [4].

2.2.2 Synthesis of goldNPs

The goldNPs were synthesized using modified tri-sodium citrate (Na₃Ct) reduction method [5]. Solutions were prepared of 0.25 mM HAuCl₄·H₂O

(solution I) and of 5% Na₃Ct (solution II). 100 ml of solution I was heated to the boiling temperature while being stirred, and 2.65 ml of solution II was added immediately. The reaction was completed when the color of solution reached a wine red. The synthesized goldNPs were dispersed in cold deionized water for further use.

2.3 Preparation of s-CNT/PS conducting balls

The preparation of composite particles is performed using a batch operated mechanofusion system (Hosokawha Micron; AMS-mini) with a motor powered at 0.75kW, a rotating speed of 1000-7000rpm [6]. Figure 1 is schematically described the mechanofusion system which consists of the fixed rounded press-head, scraper, and rotating chamber in the fixed outer chamber. The gap between the rounded press-head and the interior wall of the rotating chamber is fixed at 1mm. Polystyrene particles adopted as a host particle and the guest particles were functionalized CNTs which smoothly grinded before use. Thiolated MWCNTs (s-CNTs) coated on the PS surface at a chamber rotation speed of 2500rpm for 15min with cooling. Within 15mins, the nanotubes attached to PS surfaces creating dispersed core/shell type conducting balls.

2.4 Preparation of goldNP/s-CNT/PS conducting balls

The s-CNT/PS conducting balls self-assembled with goldNPs, forming PS-MWCNT-CO-NH-(CH₂)₂-S-goldNPs. Dropping the aqueous dispersion of the composite particles into goldNPs colloid with varies weight ratio of goldNPs to PS and leave it for 4h (Figure 2). The goldNPs were quickly and easily bonded to the surface of s-CNTs. The assembled conductive balls (goldNPs/s-CNT/PS) were sunken to bottom and supernatant was getting clear.

2.5 Preparation of goldNP/PS conducting balls

To adsorb goldNPs on the surface of PS particles, we dispersed the PS particles in the 1:1 silane coupling agent and methanol mixture (v/v) with magnetic string at 450 rpm, for 1h and then filtered solution. 1.5 % aqueous dispersion of the treated PS particles dropped into the goldNPs colloid at the same experimental condition of goldNP/ CNT/PS conductive balls.

2.6 Characterization

The different functionalized MWCNTs were characterized by x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Morphology of the colloidal goldNPs and the composite particles was observed by field-emission electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The electrical conductivity of these gold NPs decorated composite particles was measured by a four-probe method.

3 Results and discussion

The thiol functional groups were introduced for making strong chemical bonding between s-CNTs and gold NPs. After chemical modification of MWCNTs surface, the products were identified by XPS. Wide scan spectra of three products (Figure 3) shows the transformation of anchoring groups on the MWCNT surfaces. Through oxidation process, the intensity of O1s is dramatically increased (Figure 3b) and after thiolation N1s, S2s and S2p peaks are observed due to amidation reaction between carboxyl group on a-CNTs and amine group of cysteamine (Figure 3a). Detailed observation of newly formed functional groups was carried out by the XPS C1s spectra (Figure 4). Comparing the s-CNTs (Figure 4a) with a-CNTs (Figure 4b), the intensity of 288.5 eV (assigned to COOH bonds) is decreased in proportion to the increase of intensity at around 287.9 eV (assigned to CONHR bonds) as a consequence of the formation of amide bond. Also, the atomic percentage of carboxyl group is reduced from 0.076 to 0.039 at%. This reduction is similar with the concentration of amide group (0.040 at%). The difference between the reduced content of the carboxyl group and increased content of the amide group results from the C-N bond formation via non-covalently adsorbed cysteamine molecules on the CNTs.

After surface treatment of MWCNTs, the s-CNTs were mechano-chemically coated on the surface of PS particles without any chemical treatment, such as wrapping a polyelectrolyte or introducing a surface charge [7, 8]. As the inner chamber is rotated, the powder is forced towards the walls of the chamber. The particles pass through the gap between the fixed rounded press-head and the rotating chamber, and they are subjected to intense shear and compressive force [6]. These forces generate sufficient local temperature, thus the small particles (indicate s-

CNTs) are easily attached to the surface of the large particle (indicate PS particles) with very strong physical and chemical adhesion. Following these mechanism, s-CNTs were uniformly covered on the PS surfaces (Figure 5b). The cross section image of the s-CNT/PS composite (Figure 5a) demonstrate that s-CNTs are embedded into the PS surface due to strong mechanical forces mentioned above.

Next, we assembled goldNPs on s-CNTs of s-CNT/PS particles. The morphology of the goldNP-assembled particles is shown in Figure 6. Even after bath sonication for 1h, goldNPs are well dispersed on the s-CNTs surface shown as small white spots (Figure 6f) and black spots (Figure 6g and 6h) on the composite. These images indicate that the thiol groups on the surface of the s-CNTs and goldNPs make strong chemical interaction during assembly step.

The electrical conductivity of s-CNT/PS composite particle is about 1.90×10^{-2} S/cm when the weight ration of s-CNTs to PS particles is 0.12:1. When s-CNTs layer is absent and the concentration of goldNPs is insufficient, the conductive balls (Figure 6a) do not show any electrical property because the assembled nanoparticles on the PS surfaces cannot form conducting pathway. When the concentration of goldNPs is enough to fully cover the PS surface (the weight ratio of goldNPs to PS particles is 0.15:1), the electrical conductivity of the conductive balls (Figure 6c) exhibits about 7.61×10^{-1} S/cm. On the other hand, small addition of goldNPs in the s-CNT-coated PS particles can enhance the conductivity of the composites by one order of magnitude. Comparing the goldNP/PS particles with the goldNP/s-CNT/PS particles (Figure 6e) which have the same amount of gold, the conductivity of latter ones is five times higher than that of former ones due to the preformed CNT conducting layer. Therefore, we can assume that s-CNTs not only act like a binder to facilitate decoration of gold NPs but also make a pathway to overcome a tunneling barrier between the gold NPs. Although the electrical property needs to be improved, this method shows a possibility to reduce gold concentration of conductive particles with scalable process.

4 Conclusion

Through chemical functionalization of the MWCNTs surface, the thiol groups were created and characterized by XPS spectra. The conductive composite particles with goldNP/s-CNT hybrid conducting layer were fabricated as follows: (i) mechano-chemically attached s-CNTs to the PS surface by using mechanofusion system, (ii) self-assembled goldNPs on the particles via strong interaction between thiol group of the s-CNTs and goldNPs. Varying the ratio of goldNPs to PS, we compared the electrical properties of the composites. The goldNP/s-CNT/PS composites show high electrical conductivity than goldNP/PS composites at the same weight ratio of goldNPs to PS because CNT layers provide connecting pathway between goldNPs. These composites have potential to apply small or light-weight electronic packaging materials and conductive fillers.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the Nanohybrids Research Center of Korea Institute of Science and Technology (KIST). This research was also kindly supported by a grant from the Industrial technology development program of the Ministry of Knowledge Economy.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the mechanofusion system.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the simple process of preparation of AuNPs/s-CNT/PS particles.

Fig. 3. XPS spectra of wide scan: (a) thiolated, (b) carboxylated and (c) pristine MWCNTs.

Fig. 4. C1s XPS spectra of (a) thiolated and (b) carboxylated MWCNTs.

Fig. 5. Electron micrographs of s-CNT/PS composite particles: (a) TEM image of Cross section, (b) SEM image of the composites with 8wt% s-CNTs.

Fig. 6. SEM images for goldNP/PS conducting particles with low concentration (a, b) and high concentration (c, d) of goldNPs and for goldNP/s-CNT/PS conducting particles with 0.15:1 weight ratio of goldNPs to s-CNTs (e, f). TEM micrographs

of the goldNP/s-CNT/PS composites (g, h). The left sides showing magnified images.

Electrical conductivity (S/cm)		
	GoldNP/sCNT/PS	GoldNP/sCNT/PS
Weight ratio (GoldNP/PS)	0	-
	0.03	-
	0.06	-
	0.09	-
	0.15	7.61
	0.21	-

Fig. 7. Electrical conductivities of goldNPs/s-CNT/PS and goldNP/PS composites with different concentration of goldNPs.

References

- [1] Y. Yamamoto, S. Takeda, H. Shiigi and T. Nagaoka "An Electroless Plating Method for Conducting Microbeads Using Gold Nanoparticles", *Journal of the Electrochemical Society*, Vol. 154, No. 9, pp 462-466, 2007.
- [2] Mi Jung LEE, Sung-Jei Hong, and Jeong-In Han, "Development of New Method to Fabricate a Conductive Ball for an Anisotropic Conductive Film", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, Vol. 49, No. 3, pp 1300-1302, 2006.
- [3] K. E. Gecheler and H. Nishide "Advanced Nanomaterials Vol. 1", 1st edition, Wiley-VCH, 2010.
- [4] Sunmi Park, Hye Ryeong Kim, Jandee Kim, Changhoon Jung, Choong Kyun Rhee, Kihyun Kwon, Youngjun Kim, "Assembly of strands of multiwall carbon nanotubes and gold nanoparticles using alkanedithiols", *Carbon*, Vol. 49, No. 2, pp 487-494, 2011.
- [5] G. Frens, "Controlled nucleation for the regulation of the particle size in monodisperse gold suspensions", *Nature Physical Science*, Vol. 241, 20-22, 1973.
- [6] Robert Pfeffer, Rajesh N. Dave, Dongguang Wei, Michelle Ramlakhan, "Synthesis of engineered particulates with tailored properties using dry particle coating", *Powder Technology*, Vol. 117, pp 40-67, 2001.
- [7] Miguel A. Correa-Duarte, Adam Kosior, Witold Kandulski, Michael Giersig, and Luis M. Liz-Marzan, "Layer-by-Layer Assembly of Multiwall Carbon Nanotubes on Spherical Colloids", *Chemistry of Materials*, Vol. 17, pp 3268-3272, 2005.
- [8] Jiwei Cui, Yaqing Liu, Jingcheng Hao, "Multiwalled Carbon-nanotube-embedded Microcapsules and Their Electrochemical Behavior", *Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, Vol. 113, No. 10, pp 3967-3972, 2009.
- [9] Mingxue Tang, Yujun Qin, Youyou Wang and ZhiXin Guo, "Hollow Carbon Nanotube Microspheres and Hemimicrospheres", *Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, Vol. 113, No. 5, pp 1666-1671, 2009.
- [10] Giovanni Conturbia, Rita de Cassia G. Vinhas, Richard Landers, Gustavo M. S. Valente, Vitor Baranauskas, and Ana Flavia Nogueira, "Single-Wall Carbon Nanotubes Chemically Modified with Cysteamine and Their Application in Polymer Solar Cells: Influence of Chemical Modification on Device Performance", *Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*, Vol. 9, pp 5850-5859, 2009.